

Cancer Immuno- therapy

CHIRON

About **7.400 cases of cancer** are diagnosed each day in Europe. Cancer is the second leading cause of mortality after cardiovascular diseases.

Cancer-related deaths are projected to increase and without action, cancer could become the **leading cause of death in Europe by 2035.**

The lifetime risk of being diagnosed with cancer:

1 in 3 for women **1 in 2 for men**

In 2023, the EU approved **25 new cancer medicines**, which represents 1/3 of all newly approved drugs.

About **30% of cancer death** are due to these five health risks :

SMOOKING

POOR DIET

OBESITY

ALCOHOL

LACK OF
EXERCISE

Major advances in the last decade were treatments that are based on the powers of the immune system: **cancer immunotherapies.** The first one was approved by the EU in 2011.

How CHIRON contributes to fighting cancer

The immune system protects us against tumours. Immune cells are highly efficient at recognizing potentially cancerous cells and 'telling' them to commit suicide.

Therefore, tumours can only develop when a cancerous cell learns to evade the signals from the immune system.

The CHIRON project develops inhibitors that block the ability of tumours to evade one particular signal. Thereby, tumour cells become sensitive and susceptible to be killed by immune cells.

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Founded by
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